
The bond dissociation energies and bond distances for Cr₂, Mo₂ and W₂: semi-empirical approach as better as relativistic ones?

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Abstract In this work, Semi-Empirical approach (PM6) is employed to calculate the bond dissociation energies and bond lengths for the dimmers Cr₂, Mo₂ and W₂. The obtained results are compared with the available experimental values, as well as another theoretical results. It is shown that SE results are in very good agreement with the available experimental data as well as calculated relativistic results.

Keywords Chromium group, dimmers, semi-empirical, electron configuration, bond dissociation

Introduction

Group 6, Cr₂, Mo₂ and W₂, have the possibility to generate sextuple bonds involving the nd and (n + 1) orbitals, attracting a lot of interest.

Whereas Cr and Mo have a d⁵s¹ valence configuration (hence, with six unpaired electrons and the possible formation of sextuple bonds), tungsten has the configuration 4f¹⁴5d⁴6s². That is, for tungsten, at a first looking, a maximum of four meta-metal bonds must be expected. In this connection, in a previous work [1], investigating bimetallic sandwich compounds, has been pointed out the W-W sextuple bond cannot be taken for granted.

As is well known, for heavy and superheavy elements, the relativistic contribution matters [2], and must be taken into account in the molecular modelling in order to obtain theoretical results compatible with the experimental data. Besides their complexity from the theoretical point of view, even today, with the development of computers and computation tools, such calculations are not so easy from an exclusively computational point of view, and only a relatively few researchers/groups are really able/dedicated to them presently.

However, as demonstrated to PtF₆ [3], semi-empirical methods (besides their minor time computation consumption and availability) can provide reliable results.

The aim of the present work is to investigate the bond dissociation energies and bond lengths for the dimmers Cr₂, Mo₂ and W₂ by a semi-empirical approach. The obtained results are compared with the available experimental values, as well as another theoretical results.

Methodology

The dimmers Cr₂, Mo₂ and W₂ were modelled by using a semi-empirical (PM6) approach, in order to calculate the bond dissociation energies and the (metal-metal) bond distances for such species.

All dimmers were modelled with zero charge. Cr₂ was modelled with four unpaired electrons, whereas Mo₂ and W₂ were modelled with zero unpaired electrons, that is, assuming that all valence electrons are involved in bonds formation.

The obtained results are compared with the available experimental values, as well as another theoretical results [4-9].

Results and Discussion

The obtained results are summarized in Table 1. As can be verified, the SE-PM6 results are in very good agreement with the available experimental data, even for W₂, for which the relativistic contribution must be higher. In fact, as can be verified from Table 1 data, the SE-PM6 approach provides very good dissociation energy values exactly to the heavier elements dimmers.

Furthermore, the obtained results for Mo₂ and W₂ are very superior (in really better agreement with experimental data) than that obtained by the natural orbital functional theory [4].

Table 1: Bond distances and bond dissociation energies for Cr₂, Mo₂ and W₂. Experimental values are between parenthesis

dimer	M-M Bond distance/ Å	D ⁰ /eV
Cr ₂	1.65 ^a	1.11 ^a
	(1.69) ^b	(1.47 ± 0.1) ^g
	(1.53) ^d	(1.56±0.2) ^b
	1.45 ^d	1.75 ^e
	1.65 ^e	
Mo ₂	1.86 ^a	4.48 ^a
	(1.93) ^b	(4.18±0.2) ^b
	1.98 ^d	(4.476) ^d
	1.95 ^e	4.04 ^e
W ₂	2.16 ^a	4.17 ^a
	(2.01) ^c	(5 ± 1) ^c
	2.03 ^e	5.54 ± 0.41 ^f
	2.12 ^d	4.41 ^e
		5.0 ^d

^aSemi-empirical (PM6), this work; ^bref. 5; ^cref.6; ^dref.7 (supplementary data); ^eref.5 (considering the relativistic contributions); ^fref.8, based on experimental data obtained to LaIr (isoelectronic with W₂); ^gref. 9.

The agreement between the data calculated in the present work and the ones available in the literature (including experimental data) shows that the assumption considered for the modelling, that is, a double bond to Cr₂ and a quadruple bond for Mo₂ and W₂ was correct.

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